

History Enhanced Computing and Sustainability

Semi structured Interview

Version 1.0 13 Dec 2023

via MS Teams

Preamble

Turn on recording and transcription.

Ask participant to confirm agreement to recording, which will be anonymised and recording deleted after transcription.

Ask participant to confirm that they received, by email, Participant Information Sheet Participant-information-sheet HECaS v1.1.docx and that they consent to participate as stated on Consent form interview HECAs v1.0.docx

Questions

What do you recall about the history content?

What else would you have wanted to hear about?

What did you feel was relevant to you?

What did you think about the format?

Did you watch any of the videos?

What did you think about the length of the videos?

Did you prefer the videos or in person in class?

What resources did you follow up?

Do you think we should continue this for future students?

What would you change?

What other history content have you been taught in the rest of your degree course at UWE?

Is there anything else you would like to tell us about the history content?

Thank participant.

Review / edit transcript and save to Interview transcripts file

For interviewer's information. Participants may have completed the pre and post test questionnaires but these are anonymised.